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CONTRACT LABOUR IN A UNIVERSITY: SOME SOCIOLOGICAL REFLECTIONS

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Title of the Paper: CONTRACT LABOUR IN A UNIVERSITY: SOME SOCIOLOGICAL REFLECTIONS
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Prof. Amaranth. R. Das** joined as the Faculty of Sociology in 1985. He was promoted as Professor in 2004 and served as Head during 2004-2007, Chairman BOS during 2007-2010 and currently heading the Department and is also the Director of Distance Education, S.K. University. He has 20 research publications in National and International Journals. He has guided 6 Ph. D. and 9 M. Phil. scholars and currently 8 Ph. D. and 4 M. Phil. scholars are working under his guidance. He has completed three Research Projects funded by University Grants Commission. He has more than 40 Seminar Papers and has delivered more than 10 Symposia lectures in National Seminars all over south India. He has recently completed a project for the A.P. Police about Farmer's Suicides in Anantapur district. He served as External member of Board of Studies in Sociology for different Universities within and outside the State. He was awarded Meritorious Teachers award by the Government of A.P in the year 2013. His areas of research are Sociology of Education, Political sociology and Social Problems.

Abstract:

Employer and employee relationships had been one of inequality and exploitation throughout in the history of mankind. Marx fought all throughout his life to alleviate the sufferings of the labor class. As the society transformed into capitalist and post modern stages, the capitalist societies evolved various mechanisms to maximize their profits. The contract labor is the order of the day and the capitalist have conveniently have devised this system to put the labor without any long term and permanent commitment to regularize their services. This paper seeks to examin profile and their attitude towards the University and their morale.

Keywords:

Labour: Restricted category of paid

Contract: Hired for a specific task and finite period

Introduction:

Employer and employee relationships had been one of inequality and exploitation throughout in the history of mankind. Marx fought all throughout his life to alleviate the sufferings of the labor class. As the society transformed into capitalist and post modern stages, the capitalist societies

evolved various mechanisms to maximize their profits. During the process, the laborer has been drifting away from the process of production, product, and community from himself in alienation in the mindless pursuit of profit by the greedy capitalists. The labour relations and governance of Industries are dictated by the capitalists of the world. The voices and cries for revolution and socialism have vanished as whimper. In the history of human productive activities the position and status of labour and its quality and its relations with the employer had underwent transformation over the years.

The capitalism that Marx saw as exploitative did undergo tremendous metamorphosis. Marx considered classes as they existed in the process of production be it agriculture or Industrial. The most meaningful classification had come from Jurgen Habermas (1976) of the Frankfurt

school, who had classified the stages of capitalism as 1.Liberal Capitalist societies of the Nineteenth century capitalism Marx knew; 2 the next stage was that of organized capitalism of the western societies after the Marxian era; 3.then came the State Socialist Societies as Post Capitalist class societies for their political elitist disposition of means of production. The disintegration of USSR and the process of economic Reforms that ensued in the last decade of the Twentieth century ramified itself into Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization spelling glorification of the capitalist society and its neo colonialist culture.

In the name of economic austerity and structural adjustments the developing societies were asked to prune welfare measures, disinvestment from unproductive and sick industries and also to freeze appointments in the public sector and official bureaucracies. To cope up with day to day work load a new system of Contract Employment came into India as a capitalist measure. In this system the labor or employee is hired for a consolidated pay and the continuity of his tenure is not guaranteed nor any provision for pension. Employer and employee relation is not ensured purposefully to avoid long term commitment and the multinational organizations are so large that to have a

direct interaction with the employer is impossible. In most of the firms the services of personnel is sought through an agency and the agency is paid to who in turn disburses the salaries getting a commission.

Typically capitalist in nature, the employer does not have any direct link for hiring the services of the employees. The employees are supplied by an agency and the agency gets payment which they distribute to the workers. The typical American policy of 'hire and fire' operates. In the decades that followed the Institution were asked to hire people on contract basis themselves for a period of 89 days and renew for every 89 days without giving any scope for making them as permanent. The institutions, finding no other way except to run the administrative machinery, with contract employees with equal number of regular employees

In the absence of constant recruitments, organizations have now reached a point of losing all the regular employees who are retiring and leaving the contract employees to filling the offices. In the coming decades in the absence of the regularly recruited and trained employees all the organizations and bureaucracies would have only contract labour? The bureaucracies are bound to lose their professional character. The character of

contract employment has certain implications for the organizations and the society at large.

The nature of contract employment is such that the workers do not have the guarantee of their continuance of their employment and they always have the Damocles' sword of termination looming large over their heads. The payment of their salaries too is unique by receiving it from an agent who keeps on receiving a commission every month. They can never claim regularizing their services at any point of time. There is nothing like annual increment but only occasional pay hike and of late a new system of time scale has come to pave way for periodicity of wage revision at least on a consolidated mode.

The contract labor is the order of the day and the capitalist have conveniently have devised this system to put the labor without any long term and permanent commitment to regularize their services. They are hired when they are needed and dispensed when not needed. The claim to permanency and continuance cannot be made at any point of time. This being the case and condition of employment what are consequences for the individual and his family? What are the consequences for the system in terms of the morale and motivation and the society at large in terms of culture of labor and

employment and the quality of services offered by various agencies and organizations. A modest attempt is made by way of a small survey of contract employees was conducted to know their profile, attitude towards the organization.

Objective:

This paper seeks to examine the system of contract employment as it exists in an university system, their profile and their attitude towards the University and their morale.

The specific objectives of the paper are:

1. To portray different categories of Contract employees at S.K. University.
2. To draw their socio-economic profiles.
3. To examine their job satisfaction and attitude towards the organization

Method of Study:

The paper is based on exclusive survey made on the Contract employees at S.K. University. There are about 300 contract employees of various categories in different departments of the university. From among them a representative sample of 30 members were chosen for a detailed descriptive study.

Interview schedule was used to collect primary data and the secondary data was collected from administrative department.

Findings and Discussion:

1. Out of the contract employees, 73.3 are males and the rest are females.
2. The caste wise distribution of the employees shows that 50.00 per cent are from backward class 30.00 are from Scheduled castes, 16.7 per cent are from Forward castes and the least is from one is from Scheduled tribe.
3. The age wise classification of the respondents shows that, 53.3 per cent are between 18- 33 years of age. Those who are above 40 years of age are about 20. Per cent. On the whole, 80 per cent of the employees are in the age group of 18-40 years of age.
4. The levels of education of the contract employees shows that 80 per cent of them have education of above intermediate to post graduation while 13.3 per cent have primary level of education and 6.7 per cent do not have any education at all.
5. The nature of their occupations shows that 30 per cent are with technical qualifications while, the majority of them are in manual occupations.
6. The present pay drawn by these employees shows that only 6.7 per cent draw less than Rs.3000 per month and 50 per cent of them draw between Rs. 3000- Rs. 5,000 per month and about 30 per cent earn between Rs. 5,000- 10,000 per month who are in technical jobs and only 13.33 per cent earn between Rs.10, 000- 22,000 p. m who are mostly library assts.
7. Of these employees 93.3 per cent receive from banks every month.
8. Of the reasons for doing contract jobs it was reported that unemployment, to be nearer to their village and also the hope of getting regularized someday are the main reasons for doing contract jobs.
9. These employees 80 per cent of them hail from rural areas and the rest from Urban and semi urban areas.
10. The present residence shows that 70 per cent of them are in rural area and the rest are in urban area.
11. The dates of their appointments shows that 16.67 per cent have been appointed prior to 2000 and while the rest 83.33 per cent were appointed after the year 2000.
12. Of these employees, 66.7 per cent have own houses, while the others live in rented houses.
13. Among these employees, 43.3 per cent have some land in which they cultivate to supplement their income.
14. Only around 10 per cent of them who live in urban area under take some

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14. Only around 10 per cent of them who live in urban area under take some

activity to supplement their income. Those who own land which is 43.33 % try cultivation from dry lands.

15. The employees 56.7 are trying for better jobs while the rest still hope of getting regularized some day.
16. As far as their job satisfaction is concerned, 63.3 per cent expressed very much too somewhat satisfaction while 23.4 expressed little to no satisfaction.
17. The attitude scale constructed to know their attitude and loyalty towards the university revealed that:
18.
 - a) Highest average attitude score of 40 was registered for those employees who were above 49 years more so due to their age and experience in the organization and the youngster's class's who are in the age of 18-25 who had joined recently. The rest did not manifest higher attitude scores.
 - b) The employees belonging to backward classes showed higher attitude scores followed by forward castes and Scs.
 - c) The employees with primary education showed higher attitude scores than others.
 - d) The Computer operators Hostel employees showed higher averages than other employees.

Conclusion:

By way of summarizing it can be said that the system of contract employment has come to stay as the mode of recruitment to organizations like the university. This system has ruined the systematic recruitment prevalent earlier through employment. Now politicians and other influential people play key role in pushing their vested interests into these organizations. Their numbers are swelling constantly, they are likely to outnumber the regular employees in near future. These employees for the lower level jobs would be suitable but certainly not for other positions such as technical and professional positions that of teachers. It can be said that the system of contract employment though sounds economically viable yet the quality of work and the morale of the employees is certainly not in the best interest of the organization. The financial crunch that the universities are facing certainly would spell doom for these workers. From the point of view of the organization, in the absence of regular recruitment and the benefits for the employees would spell doom in the coming decades. The large strength of contract employees on the roll might trigger frequent strikes and union movement to threaten the institution. On

the whole contract appointment might be an adhoc mechanism for manual and other small jobs and not definitely for technical and professional positions in any organization like a university

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Appendix:

Table No. 1

Gender wise distribution of Contract Employees

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	22	73.3
Female	8	26.7
Total	30	100.0

Table No. II

Caste wise distribution of Contract Employees

Caste	Frequency	Percent
Forward Castes	5	16.7
Backward Classes	15	50.0
Scheduled Castes	9	30.0
Scheduled Tribes	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

Table No III.

Age wise Distribution of Contract Employees

Age	Frequency	Percent
18 - 25	4	13.3
26 - 33	12	40.0
34 - 40	8	26.7
41 - 48	2	6.7
49 >	4	13.3
Total	30	100.0

Table No. IV

Educational levels of Contract Employees.

Level of Education	Frequency	Percent
No Schooling	2	6.7
Primary School	4	13.3
Secondary School	4	13.3
Intermediate	1	3.3
Degree	12	40.0
Post Degree	7	23.3
Total	30	100.0

Table No. V

Occupational Distribution of Contract Employees

Nature of Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Assistant Cook	1	3.3
Attender	11	36.7
Computer Operator	6	20.0
Driver	1	3.3
Hostel Worker	3	9.9
Lab Assistant	1	3.3
Library Asst	4	10.0
Sweeper	1	3.3
Watchman	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0

Table No. VI

Present Pay drawn by Contact Employees

Pay	Frequency	Percent
Rs. 1500	1	3.3
2500	1	3.3
3850	1	3.3
3900	12	40.0
4000	2	6.7
6000	6	20.0
7000	1	3.3
7150	1	3.3
8000	1	3.3
13000	1	3.3
15000	1	3.3
19000	1	3.3
22000	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

Table No.VII

Age and Average Attitude Scores of Contract Employees

Age	No of Employees	Average Attitude Score
18 -25	4	37.0
26 -31	12	33.8
34 -40	8	36.9
41 - 48	2	32.0
49 >	4	40.0

Table No. VIII

Caste and Average Attitude Scores of Contract Employees

Caste	No of Employees	Average Attitude Score
Forward Castes	5	34.8
Backward Castes	15	37.3
Scheduled Castes	9	34.1
Scheduled Tribe	1	30.0

Table No. IX
Level of Education and Average
Attitude Scores of Contract Employees

Education Level	No. of Employees	Average Attitude Score
No Schooling	2	36.5
Primary Education	4	38.2
Secondary Education	4	32.2
Inter	1	37.0
Degree	12	36.4
P G	7	34.8

Table No. X
Type of Job and Average Attitude
Scores of Contract Employees

Nature of Occupation	No. of Employees	Average Attitude Score
Assistant Cook	1	36.0
Attender	11	35.9
Computer Operator	6	41.2
Driver	1	37.0
Hostel Worker	3	40.3
Lab Assistant	1	32.0
Library Asst	4	36.2
Sweeper	1	27.0
Watchman	2	39.0